

COMPOSING ‘EATEN ALIVE’: EXPLORING THE INTERSECTION OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLOBAL FISH PRODUCTION THROUGH SONIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The climate crisis has become one of the most pressing existential issues facing humankind. In a past era, the connection between ocean health and life on Earth might have been less clear. Today, however, the evidence pointing to the ocean’s vital role in sustaining planetary life is undeniable. The mass extraction of fish since the burgeoning of the fishing industry in the twentieth century has had a devastating impact on the ocean’s biodiversity and ecosystem. The composition ‘Eaten Alive for String Quintet, Tape, and Electronics Processing’ sonifies the intersection of climate change and global fish production. The process of composing the piece unfolded through: (1) gathering existing research describing the relationship between these two phenomena, (2) developing the compositional concept and sourcing the relevant datasets, (3) programming a sonification tool that would both satisfy the requirements of the piece’s framework and support the expression of musical aesthetics, and (4) composing ‘Eaten Alive.’ The composition represents the author’s attempt at bringing awareness to the relationship between climate change and global fish production through musical sonification. The process and considerations behind the data sonification and composition of the work are detailed in this paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

The climate crisis alarm has been sounding for decades. In 1965, U.S. President Lyndon B. Johnson’s advisory board wrote, “pollutants have altered on a global scale the carbon dioxide content of the air” leading to effects that “could be deleterious from the point of view of human beings.” [1] Despite nonstop warnings for more than 50 years and having failed to sufficiently alter our present trajectory, the planet has begun to experience unprecedented numbers of life-threatening weather conditions. The causes and potential solutions to this catastrophe are many – yet why does the ocean, one of the Earth’s major carbon sinks [2], seldom find itself at the center of mainstream discussion?

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According to the United Nations Environment Programme: “Oceans, and all marine life that lives under and above the water, play a central role in stabilizing the Earth’s climate. They provide a vital source of food to a vast number of land and water species and regulate the amount of CO₂ (carbon dioxide) that stays in the atmosphere by absorbing 30 percent of global emissions.” [3] The ocean’s ecosystem and biodiversity are of vital importance in its ability to absorb carbon dioxide and produce oxygen. Sylvia Earle (former Chief Scientist of the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) and John Bridgeland (former Director of the U.S. Domestic Policy Council) write, “Since the 1950s, half of the coral reefs, much of the phytoplankton, and 90 percent of many kinds of fish in the sea [...] have been extracted as commodities. While fishing to feed populations and sustain economies is critical, technologies have been applied to finding, catching and marketing ocean wildlife on a scale that is both unprecedented and unsustainable. [...] Climate policies take into account the release of carbon dioxide when a forest is cut or burned, and the losses caused by destruction of terrestrial systems that naturally sequester carbon. But where on the balance sheet is an accounting of losses incurred by industrial fishing that clear-cut ocean systems [...]?” [4] While the science seems to acknowledge the correlation between climate change and global fish production, fish capture has doubled globally since 1990 which may indicate a lack of public awareness regarding the issue. [5]

For a composer, data sonification techniques can be useful in bringing awareness to social issues through music. For example, in her work ‘Heat and the Heartbeat of the City’ Andrea Polli uses temperature data from Central Park to illustrate the current and predicted impacts of climate change on the residents of New York City. [6] Over the course of the work, the intensity of the sonified data increases, reflecting the number of consecutive days of extreme heat. Matthew Burtner, a native of Alaska, draws awareness to glacial melt in his composition ‘Elegy (Muir Glacier 1889-2009).’ [7] Recordings of melting glaciers are intertwined throughout the work which elucidates another dimension of the data’s origin. Chris Chafe and Greg Niemeyer’s ‘Smog Music’ sonifies smog data from approximately two dozen cities around world. [8] In contrast to the Polli and Burtner, this piece was composed for instrumentalists which, perhaps, creates a different experience

Figure 1. Global temperature change 1961-2020.

than a digitally conjured sonification. Each of these sonification pieces utilize techniques (sonic intensity for expressive impact, inclusion of related audio recordings, and performance by instrumentalists) that have been implemented within ‘Eaten Alive for String Quintet, Tape, and Electronics Processing.’¹ This composition, similar to the aforementioned works, attempts to bring awareness to planetary health, specifically the relationship between global fish production and climate change. ‘Eaten Alive’ is conceived as a fixed-media video performance, common for music created during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns. It is scheduled to be premiered at the Technosonics festival at the University of Virginia in February 2023.

2. STRUCTURING THE COMPOSITION

2.1 Representing the Two Datasets

As increased musical pitch can often signify suspense, tension, or drama within a composition, it was determined that the climate data would be represented in the frequency (or pitch) domain, with lower temperatures being represented by lower pitches and higher temperatures by higher pitches. Because this work is intended to depict the harm that global fish extraction enacts on the oceans (and by extension the planet), fish production was chosen to be represented by a spectral filter and delay effects processing, which, when applied to the recorded string quintet, would degrade the fidelity of the recordings. That is to say, the greater the amount of fishing, the greater the degradation of the string quintet sound.

2.2 Data Sourcing

The climate dataset was sourced from The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations [9] website and was available in monthly increments from 1961 through 2020 (Fig. 1). The fishing data was sourced from the Our World In Data [5] website and was available from 1960 to 2018 in yearly increments (Fig. 2). With the mid-20th century signaling a dramatic rise in both climate change

¹ ‘Eaten Alive’ video performance: <https://youtu.be/diqBjdQohv8> and score: <https://www.scribd.com/document/591685665/Eaten-Alive>

Figure 2. Global fish capture 1960-2018.

and global fish production, this date range was sufficient. As each dataset was subdivided by country, the decision was made to consolidate the data roughly by continent in order to accommodate a string quintet: Oceania and Australia would be represented by Violin 1, Europe by Violin 2, Asia by Viola 1, the Americas by Viola 2, and Africa by the Cello. Next, the climate data was scaled to the range of its respective instrument (represented by MIDI values). The fishing data was normalized to a 0-1 scale for controlling the effects processing amount.

2.3 Compositional Considerations

Four considerations were identified at the outset of the composing process:

(1) One of the challenges when sonifying data that is sampled at periodic intervals is that, when musically represented, its rhythm sounds like a barrage of quarter or eighth notes. In order to create rhythmic variation, a Pure Data (PD) patch (detailed in Section 3) was created that would average data samples into longer notes, thereby creating the possibility for sustained notes of varying lengths. Besides being able to turn this feature on and off, the number of notes being averaged, or window size, would be dynamic.

(2) It would be important for the PD patch to have the capability to not only create longer (averaged) notes but also be able to hear the composition as the note lengths were being shaped. This way, compositional decisions could be auditioned on the fly, allowing for a flexible and creative workspace. This would allow the composition to be shaped, thereby reflecting the intensity of our climate trajectory. For example, Earth Day was established in 1970 to bolster public awareness of environmental pollution, thus the rhythmic activity of the score after 1970 increases.

(3) It was decided to allow for a variable-speed data playback rate. In effect, some months and years would pass by slower or faster than others. A film plot might span many years; however, the director may choose to spend more time focusing on certain dramatic points than others. To realize this concept within ‘Eaten Alive,’ a variable-speed data playback rate was incorporated into the patch.

(4) In order to illustrate the transformation of climate awareness over time, ‘Eaten Alive’ would also include au-

dio clips of news reports and scientists over the past 60 years that narrate this history. The dates of these clips are synchronized to the sonification playback, thereby creating a connection with their time period. The variable-speed playback allows the composition to focus in on some of these periods of dynamic change and zoom out during other time spans.

3. REALIZING DATABUMp – A CUSTOM-BUILT SONIFICATION PATCH IN PD

Two overarching goals were identified when designing DatabuMp²: (1) create a simple, yet effective, GUI interface to allow the composition process to unfold as naturally as possible and, (2) enable the software to encapsulate the entire scope of the composition process by both sonifying the datasets into a note-based score and applying the effects processing to the recorded stems. Figure 3 depicts the composition process shaped by DatabuMp.

3.1 Automation-based Approach

Drawing inspiration from traditional digital audio workstations (DAWs) such as Ableton Live or Pro Tools, it was decided to model DatabuMp on a track-based automation system (Fig. 4). The variable-speed data playback rate is set by a main automation lane (named “Metro”). Each instrument is assigned two automation lanes: (1) the zoom amount (i.e. the window size, or the number of data points that are averaged into one note) and (2) the mode of operation, of which there are three options: Normal, Moving Average, and Quantized Average. “Normal” indicates there is no averaging and the data is sonified directly from the scaled dataset. With “Moving Average” the average is recalculated at each new datapoint and effectively smooths out the stream of notes. “Quantized Average” calculates the average once at the beginning of each new window – this creates longer notes. Automation is integral to this compositional approach; averaging modes and window sizes can be continually changing, thereby creating a dynamic composition while faithfully representing the data. In addition, automation can be recorded on the fly, giving the composer the ability to react to and re-shape the composition while listening to playback.

In many cases, the composition process can take days, weeks or even months. The DatabuMp GUI provides access to features that have been implemented to streamline this process, allowing the composer to focus on shaping the data into a musical composition. These features allow for the following capabilities: save automation data in order to continue composing at a later time, change the point of playback (i.e. move the ‘playback head’ to the end or middle of the composition), quantize note lengths to a specific BPM (beats per minute) so notes will align to the desired grid within notation software, and calculate the length of the composition (which can change dramatically depending on the rate of data playback). Additional features are configurable by editing a text file within the

² DatabuMp GitHub: <https://github.com/brianlindgren/DatabuMp>

Figure 3. Composition process from beginning to end.

Figure 4. DatabuMp’s track-based automation.

DatabuMp folder. These include the ability to: set the automation lane minimum and maximum values; change the ratio of note data playback to effects processing data playback (in the case of ‘Eaten Alive’ the climate change data was sampled monthly while the fishing data was sampled yearly, thus requiring a 12:1 playback ratio); set the intensity of the effects processing; and specify the types of note lengths available to the quantization engine (e.g. quarter note triplets, thirty-second notes, etc.).

3.2 Modular System

With the intention to allow for any number of instruments, DatabuMp is a modular system. When adding or subtracting an instrument, the automation, playback, and effects processing modules can be dynamically created or removed. The software is designed to be adaptable for future compositions.

4. COMPOSING ‘EATEN ALIVE’

After sourcing the data, outlining the compositional concept, and building the software, the next step was to begin composing ‘Eaten Alive.’ While the preparation phase was conducted over the course of several weeks, the composing process took a few days. The software performed its primary task well: DatabuMp allowed for a focused and

streamlined composition process. Working with the automation lanes felt ‘natural’ and the composer was able to ‘get in the zone.’

4.1 Working Within DatabuMp

As with any artistic process, there is a back-and-forth response between the artist and the medium. At the outset of the composition process, both the sound of the raw data and the conceptual material (the sonified data and the historic audio clips) evoked certain feelings. To illustrate, the sonified data in the early 1960s created consonant harmonies at some moments and dissonant harmonies at others, evoking emotions teetering between suspense and resolution. DatabuMp was used to contour longer notes that accentuated these harmonic qualities.

As the composing process unfolded, the raw data was shaped using automation to create longer (averaged) notes. This allowed for both sparsely spaced notes, which depicted feelings of uncertainty reflected in the awareness of climate change at the time, and also longer phrases that created a gradual dramatic unfolding as the composition developed. As this material was played back (using either raw sine tones or MIDI strings) it inspired further tweaking and adjusting. For example, the growing public awareness of climate change in the 1980s is depicted by a dissonant melody played by the second violin and an unyielding *pizzicato* duel between the violas. Seasonal cycles and other weather phenomena such as erratic temperature fluctuations created natural sensations of tension and release within the work.

As the audio clips were added into playback (DatabuMp playback was synced with Ableton Live via MIDI), new ideas were conjured and the notes were further shaped. For instance, over the course of the piece, the spoken content of the audio clips becomes progressively urgent due to the increasing severity of climate change. Because global temperatures are rising, the sonified data rises higher and higher in pitch as the composition unfolds, creating an increasing intensity. Toward the end, it was decided to slow the rate of playback significantly, in effect, depicting the perception of time slowing down at a moment of calamity or crisis. ‘Eaten Alive’ culminates in a *fortissimo* within the upper range of each instrument’s register, accompanied by an audio clip of reporters ardently describing the disastrous California wildfires of 2019.

4.2 Moving into the Notation Environment

Next, the notes were recorded via the IAC driver (Inter-Application Communication on macOS) into Live first and then exported to MuseScore. Because each month had a corresponding temperature value (no month had a blank value) there were no musical rests in the composition. Miles Davis once allegedly said, “In music, silence is more important than sound.” The artistic decision was made to shorten many of the notes (without shifting the subsequent note ahead), thereby creating all-important silence (rests) as well as notes of varying lengths. This was approached with the intention of shaping expressive instrumental reactions to the unfolding events of this decades-long cli-

Figure 5. Example of thematic material in ‘Eaten Alive’.

mate drama. Sometimes these choices created recurring thematic ideas (Fig. 5) and other times not. Articulations and dynamics were added to support both the thematic material and expressive musical gestures. Once the score was completed, it was recorded with each instrument individually miked.

4.3 Adding Effects Processing With DatabuMp

Lastly, the audio stems were imported into DatabuMp for effects processing. In the processing signal chain, the audio is first run through a spectral filter and then through a spectral delay. In the spectral filter, each frequency bin is boosted or attenuated by a random amplitude, but maximally limited at the value of fish production that year. Similarly, each frequency bin in the spectral delay is delayed by a random time value, but limited to the fishing value of that year. The result is that as fish production increases, the audio fidelity is increasingly degraded, sounding unstable and askew. The intensity of the effects processing was tweaked until satisfaction was achieved via the editable configuration file.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper details the process of sonifying climate change and global fish production data into the composition ‘Eaten Alive for String Quintet, Tape, and Electronics Processing.’ Sonification can be a powerful tool for transforming data into artistic material and thereby helping to decipher meaning behind otherwise mysterious numbers. By the author’s assessment this work represents a provocative musical depiction of two consequential datasets. The sonification, incorporated with historic audio clips, narrates a winding yet unmistakable trajectory brought about by disregard for the health of our ocean systems. While the rising pitch creates an expected increase in musical intensity, the addition of effects processing has a surprisingly persuasive effect in underscoring the intersection of climate change and global fish production. However, the premiere next year will function as a meaningful test in determining the work’s impact. It is the hope of the author that ‘Eaten Alive’ will make a contribution, no matter how small, in understanding and rectifying our planet’s current climate catastrophe.

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